

Evaluating MODULAIR gas measurements against EPA's Air Sensor Performance Targets

This document summarizes an evaluation performed by QuantAQ to document how MODULAIR gas measurements perform relative to EPA's Air Sensor Performance targets.

The US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) released Air Sensor Performance Targets for gas sensors across two reports in 2021 and 2023^{1,2}. Here, we present a meta-analysis of MODULAIR performance using NSIM (Non-regulatory Supplemental and Informational Monitoring) guidelines and evaluation metrics at locations across the world. This summary document covers QuantAQ's 2024 model release which were made available to customers beginning in Q4 of 2024. The MODULAIR meets or exceeds NSIM targets for CO while slightly missing for NO₂ and O₃. NO is included in this report, though there are no EPA NSIM performance targets for NO.

Metric		CO	O ₃	NO*	NO ₂
Bias	Slope	0.85	1.1	0.94	0.80
	Intercept (ppbv)	25.1	0.6	1.4	4.6
Linearity	Pearson R ²	0.87	0.90	0.85	0.64
Precision	SD (ppbv)	15.2	3.0	2.6	1.5
	Coef. of Variation (%)	5.4	10.3	61.2	12.7
Error	MAE (ppbv)	64.5	4.5	3.0	4.3
	RMSE (ppbv)	84.3	5.9	5.0	5.7

Table 1. US EPA NSIM target summary table. All metrics shown in black text for CO, O₃, and NO₂ meet or exceed expected quality standards set by EPA. *NO is not a criteria pollutant and NSIM standards are not set by EPA; however, we have listed the evaluation metrics using the same guidelines. Values shown in red text did not meet EPA NSIM standards; only the RMSE for O₃ and NO₂ currently do not meet NSIM standards (target is < 5 ppb for O₃).

Data and Methodology

Data used in this evaluation were gathered from long-running co-location studies from the United States and the United Kingdom. All data used are from previously unseen MODULAIR sensors and locations that represent various environments that differ in climate and pollutant ranges. All reference data are from US EPA FEM-grade reference monitors, though the exact make and model vary site-to-site. Each co-location met or exceeded EPA NSIM site criteria requirements for its pollutant. A summary of the test sites and data used in this evaluation can be found in Table 2.

Climate	Test Sites / Devices / Number of Records			
	CO	O ₃	NO	NO ₂
US Northeast	2 / 6 / 15.5k	2 / 5 / 11.8k	2 / 6 / 15.5k	3 / 8 / 19.6k
US Northwest	1 / 1 / 865	-	1 / 1 / 865	1 / 1 / 865
UK Southwest	-	-	2 / 2 / 1378	1 / 2 / 730

Table 2. Data locations and availability. Data locations are described by country and region to provide context around environmental conditions. The number of records represents the number of hourly data records used in the evaluation from that location.

The devices used in this evaluation followed the same calibration process used across all QuantAQ products. Before shipment, each MODULAIR undergoes a laboratory-based calibration where sensors are placed in our environmental chamber and undergo a multi-point calibration using known concentrations of target gases. Concentrations are verified using a suite of Teledyne gas analyzers (T300, T200U, T100, T400) which are calibrated and maintained according to the manufacturer’s specifications. Sensor calibration parameters are recorded and fed into gas-specific global models that incorporate knowledge about how specific electrochemical sensors respond to different environments and cross-sensitivities.

Figure 1. QuantAQ gas sensors undergo a multi-step process to produce final concentration readings.

Model Details

For each target analyte, we provide a brief description and site-specific evaluations. Marker color indicates location and marker shape indicates the broader climate region. The NSIM evaluation metrics are calculated for each sensor at each site and then aggregated. We aggregate by site rather than by individual sensor; in other words, if location 1 has ten sensors and location 2 has 1 sensor, the sensors at location 1 count 1/10 as much in the overall aggregation as the sensor at location 2. We have chosen this approach as we believe it is more representative of what you can expect to see if deploying your sensor in a completely new location.

Carbon Monoxide (CO)

Our CO model is a multiple linear regression (MLR) model fit using ordinary least squares (OLS). Each unit is calibrated against a NIST-traceable standard reference gas under laboratory conditions.

Figure 2. CO performance against EPA NSIM guidelines. The subplot on the left shows results for linearity and error and the subplot on the right shows results for bias. Bounding boxes, shown in green, indicate the range that meets or exceeds NSIM guidelines.

Below, we list the US EPA NSIM guidelines and results for CO.

		NSIM Target	Reported	Result
Precision	Standard Dev. (ppbv)	≤ 20	15.2	PASS
	Coef. of Variation (%)	≤ 30	5.4	PASS
Bias	Slope	1.0 ± 0.2	0.85	PASS
	Intercept (ppbv)	-50 ≤ b ≤ 50	25.1	PASS
Linearity	Pearson R ²	≥ 0.80	0.87	PASS
Error	RMSE (ppbv)	≤ 150	84.3	PASS

Our CO sensor meets or exceeds all EPA NSIM guidelines.

Ozone (O₃)

Our O₃ model is a feed-forward neural network trained with the Adam optimizer with 100 hidden nodes and the ReLU activation function. Each unit is calibrated against a NIST-traceable standard reference gas under laboratory conditions.

Figure 3. O₃ performance against EPA NSIM guidelines. The subplot on the left shows results for linearity and error and the subplot on the right shows results for bias. Bounding boxes, shown in green, indicate the range that meets or exceeds NSIM guidelines.

Below, we list the US EPA NSIM guidelines and results for O₃.

		NSIM Target	Reported	Result
Precision	Standard Dev. (ppbv)	≤ 5	3.0	PASS
	Coef. of Variation (%)	≤ 30	10.3	PASS
Bias	Slope	1.0 ± 0.2	1.1	PASS
	Intercept (ppbv)	-5 ≤ b ≤ 5	0.56	PASS
Linearity	Pearson R ²	≥ 0.80	0.90	PASS
Error	RMSE (ppbv)	≤ 5	5.9	FAIL

Our O₃ sensor **does not meet or exceed EPA NSIM guidelines** due to the RMSE failing to meet the threshold set by EPA, largely due to results found at a single location.

Nitric Oxide (NO)

Our NO model is a stacked regression that leverages a multiple linear regression at low temperatures and a hybrid regression³ at higher temperatures. The hybrid regression algorithm combines a multilayer perceptron (MLP) model with a multiple linear regression which is optimized with a custom objective. The MLP consists of two layers with the ReLU activation function, optimized with Adam, and trained with early stopping. Each unit is calibrated against a NIST-traceable standard reference gas under laboratory conditions.

^{3,4}

Figure 4. NO performance using the same methodology used for other gases and NSIM guidelines. Note, there are no EPA NSIM guidelines for NO. The subplot on the left shows results for linearity and error and the subplot on the right shows results for bias. There are no bounding boxes for NO as there are no NSIM guidelines for NO.

Below, we list the results for NO, though there are no official NSIM guidelines.

		NSIM Target	Reported	Result
Precision	Standard Dev. (ppbv)	NA	2.6	
	Coef. of Variation (%)	NA	61.2	
Bias	Slope	NA	0.94	
	Intercept (ppbv)	NA	1.4	
Linearity	Pearson R ²	NA	0.85	
Error	RMSE (ppbv)	NA	5.0	

Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂)

The NO₂ model is a hybrid of two regression models³. The first is a multiple linear regression (MLR) model fit using ordinary least squares (OLS). The second is a multilayer perceptron with two layers and the tanh activation function, optimized with Adam and trained with early stopping. Each unit is calibrated against a NIST-traceable standard reference gas under laboratory conditions.

Figure 5. NO₂ performance against US EPA NSIM guidelines. The subplot on the left shows results for linearity and error and the subplot on the right shows results for bias. Bounding boxes, shown in green, indicate the range that meets or exceeds NSIM guidelines.

Below, we list the US EPA NSIM guidelines and results for NO₂.

		NSIM Target	Reported	Result
Precision	Standard Dev. (ppbv)	≤ 5	1.5	PASS
	Coef. of Variation (%)	≤ 30	12.7	PASS
Bias	Slope	1.0 ± 0.35	0.80	PASS
	Intercept (ppbv)	-5 ≤ b ≤ 5	4.6	PASS
Linearity	Pearson R ²	≥ 0.70	0.64	FAIL
Error	RMSE (ppbv)	≤ 15	5.7	PASS

Our NO₂ sensor **does not meet or exceed EPA NSIM guidelines** due to the Pearson R² failing to meet the threshold set by EPA.

Citing this document

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Changelog

- 2024.12.14 Corrected an error in the NO₂ summary Table
- 2024.12.01 NO and NO₂ models revised. Figures and charts updated to restrict evaluations to co-locations that meet EPA NSIM site criteria.
- 2024.04.29 This is the first release of QAN 004.